

Discussion Breakout 1 Room Assignments

- **Breakout Room A (2E39):** NASA processes vs collaborative platform: how to use collaborative platforms when the source code is closed.
- **Breakout Room B (2L78):** Incentives for cross-project collaboration Need for new funding models that are not mission-based. Recognize the software infrastructure that goes beyond/across individual missions.
- **Breakout Room C (2R69):** Need for a means of cross-SMD discovery of common software functionality/needs to facilitate collaboration. Defining incentives for cross project collaboration on shared software.
- **Breakout Room D (4W55):** The need to transition from local-based computer development/analysis to remote/cloud platforms. New tools need to be developed to transition scientists to working in the cloud as easily as working locally. This means tools, IDEs, and data formats.
- **Breakout Room E (MIC 3A-3H42A):** There is a desire to bridge NASA open source efforts and the broader community. NASA can benefit from the work of the community, and NASA can make significant contributions to public code.

Discussion Breakout 2 Room Assignments

- **Breakout Room A (2E39):** What workshops would be useful? Examples: Cross-science for one type of software, cross-agency for one type of software, cross software for one science division, etc.
- **Breakout Room B (2L78):** Clear guidance for scientists and software engineers on NASA policy related to software.
- **Breakout Room C (2R69):** Hack on software section of the Open Science Guidance for scientists or for missions.
- **Breakout Room D (4W55):** What gaps are there in software funding?
- **Breakout Room E (MIC 3A-3H42A):** How do we foster communities to continue software collaboration? More communities!

Topic 1B: Incentives for cross-project collaboration

1. Whatever we do, the focus should be on fostering communities. Regular meetings help, but need the developers as well as the managers (rotating?)
 - a. Goal of incentivizing collaboration and community building is to reduce wasted time and money by encouraging reuse so that we build new things and not the same things over and over. Creating the kind of collaborative environment in the software community that exists in the (highly connected) science community
2. Core software is where the communities can thrive and core capabilities emerge from the community. Need to be fostered not forced.
3. Raise the profile of software AND the associated communities with senior leadership (e.g. “decadal” (3 years?) survey). Leadership needs to recognize the value of community volunteership (even though it’s messy at times)

Topic 1B: (virtual)

This session's focus was: incentives for cross-project collaboration; need for new funding models that are not mission-based; recognizing the software infrastructure that goes beyond missions.

Takeaways:

1. Mission operation software needs to increase last mile support (requirements, funding emphasis, or cross mission work)
 - a. Last mile defined data access/analysis software (data that comes out of the mission)
2. Have HQ create an easier way to funds to be distributed across centers so we incentivize cross-mission support
 - a. Across centers and even externally
3. Incorporating these into grant reviewer rubrics to show in the funding the project's reusability and active use

Topic 1C:

This session's focus is: Need for a means of cross-SMD discovery of common software functionality/needs to facilitate collaboration. Defining incentives for cross project collaboration on shared software.

1. There should be a software discovery page that can link/search across all the different software repositories for NASA open-source software projects. There are several ways the NASA software catalog could be improved. These include subcategories for each top category, mandatory, visible, and curated tags/labels, and additional summary info for each project such as POCs, and successful applications allowing cross-comparisons between tools.
2. Workshops/hackathons to demo/introduce NASA software projects to bring the various SMD communities together to encourage collaborations and new teaming arrangements
3. NASA specifies three launch vehicles. Likewise, NASA could specify 3-5 software projects to accomplish a mission need, (e.g., science data processing), and if the project does something different, they have to justify their decision (i.e., why the existing solutions aren't adequate).
4. Specific funding calls for cross-SMD projects with >\$150K.

Topic 1C (Virtual):

This session's focus is: Need for a means of cross-SMD discovery of common software functionality/needs to facilitate collaboration. Defining incentives for cross project collaboration on shared software

1. A better software catalog that allows someone to determine if what they are working on already exists out there, or to find collaboration opportunities
2. Increase cross-collaborational events between NASA division leads with HQ and make sure whatever plans are developed are shared at lower levels of NASA workforce so that we can implement the plan at our organizations and within our projects/labs.

Topic 1D (onsite): The need to transition from local-based computer development/analysis to remote/cloud platforms. New tools need to be developed to transition scientists to working in the cloud as easily as working locally. This means tools, IDEs, and data formats.

1. For the cloud to be effective, we need to better ensure that files on there are cloud-optimized, otherwise users may not experience the best of the cloud. Encourage open source software to help massively convert.
2. Community: Create a unified voice through collaboration to determine best practices, what the cloud landscape looks like in the future
3. Education/Training. Center of Excellence. Technology solutions to the problems raised are already there. Training is needed at all levels (users, developers, scientists, decision makers) in the use of E4S (Extreme Scale Scientific Software Stack) and other cloud technologies. Credentials

Topic 1D (virtual): The need to transition from local-based computer development/analysis to remote/cloud platforms. New tools need to be developed to transition scientists to working in the cloud as easily as working locally. This means tools, IDEs, and data formats.

1. Cloud themes: science in browser, to interact with data in the cloud. Jupyter. Easy to manage. Reproducible.
2. Recommendation: explore the post-Jupyter IDE/tooling: Jupyter good for exploration but not devops, so what next? Want to keep science-on-browser with access to cloud data, but a better Integrated Development Environment.
3. With HPC resources (undersubscribed), is there an incentive for people to move to cloud vs using on-prem? Need for champions.

Topic 1E: There is a desire to bridge NASA open source efforts and the broader community. NASA can benefit from the work of the community, and NASA can make significant contributions to public code.

1. Continue reducing the barriers for NASA people to contribute to outside projects.
2. Document and publicize open source success stories. Examples of how to do things.
3. Reevaluate the strategy for how we advertise NASA codes and data? Is a catalog an effective way to do it?

Topic 2A: What workshops would be useful?

1. Whatever we do costs money. To make it worthwhile whoever goes must share what they learned to their group when they return
2. Attach to existing science meetings and/or combine existing meetings
 - a. Foster purposeful collisions between existing meetings and have an overlap day to cover higher level topics relevant to software in all areas
3. Have a two phase workshop spread over time – 1. Define the problem, 2. Solve the problem

Topic 2A (Virtual): What workshops would be useful?

This session's focus is: What workshops would be useful? Examples: Cross-science for one type of software, cross-agency for one type of software, cross software for one science division, etc.

1. Workshops we identified: mission operation software, and software engineering in the cloud.
2. Workshop for people who are part-scientist, part-engineer. Someone who works with both and is interested in both. You have to be an engineer to do science at scale these days. An example would be the Planetary Data Workshop.
3. Have a workshop that combines multiple topics but segregated by days: first half of the week focus on mission software, then second half on cloud etc. This is to minimize travel and planning efforts. Workshops that are organized within and outside centers.

Topic 2B:

This sessions focus is: Clear guidance for scientists and software engineers on NASA policy related to software.

1. Clear guidance on how NASA engineers can contribute to open source projects.
2. Provide software engineering education (like TOPS training) rather than requiring software engineering compliance for science and open source projects. Work toward a vision of software engineering practices and instructional material that are so good that other projects voluntarily adopt them.
3. Restrictive center variations in software release policies impede productivity and community contributions.

Topic 2B (virtual): Clear guidance for scientists and software engineers on NASA policy related to software.

Takeaways:

1. The need for examples in different types of software policy compliance (open and closed, research, third party tools, etc)
 - a. Which policies need to be followed for the different types of software
 - b. Examples of what following these policies look like (e.g. how required documents should be filled out)
2. Greater efficiency in timelines (make more conducive to funding cycles and the open source culture); open source development defined to the community vs the legal department
 - a. The longest office in the request process is legal- what can HQ do to speed this up?
 - b. Train legal in open source policies/processes! Or hire someone who can.
 - c. Is there a way to speed up review of dependencies of libraries used in software?
3. Having different processes based on type/class of software being released
 - a. The one-size fits all approach to SRS is not working, there should be different processes based on different classes/types of software.

Topic 2C: (onsite and virtual)

This session's focus was: Hack on software section of the Open Science Guidance for scientists or for missions.

Ease of learning and adoption:

1. Creating a TL;DR for the guidance a “Basic How To?” with checklists for minimum requirements and how to go above and beyond, with examples

Establishing better ownership models:

1. Why it's helpful to you? Including a motivation component and reasoning, on why implementation of such policies is useful for research, etc.
2. What not to fear? Clear requirements and responsibilities when you create an open source project, minimizing unfunded expectations/management. And you can share code that was written in proprietary software (for example, MatLab).

Topic 2D (onsite): What gaps are there in software funding?

1. NASA doesn't treat software as a capability, and should.
 - a. An example of something NASA does treat as a capability and dedicates funding to is the DSN.
 - b. This implies there should be built-in funding for identified core critical capabilities.
2. Look outside: We need to look at other private companies and government agencies that treat software more as infrastructure and a core capability and fund it accordingly.
3. There are gaps between the HPOSS opportunity and other software opportunities (like SOSS and OSTFL) that fund more mature libraries. Also HPOSS is frequently not enough funding to actually get started effectively.
4. \$\$\$\$\$\$\$
5. Funding opportunities across Divisions are not consistent.

Topic 2D (virtual): What gaps are there in software funding?

1. Software is not hardware, it is organic and needs a different model. You often don't know which components will be OS-reusable until later in the dev cycle.
2. Reward multi-mission or code reuse by making it part of the selection criteria.
3. Modernizing Legacy Black Box Software needs to be a priority.
4. Continue OS funding but don't require it be tied to a current grant/mission nor a singular science goal.

Topic 2E: How do we foster communities to continue software collaboration? More communities!

1. NASA funding calls should explicitly allow and encourage the use of grant funds for community development activities (travel, time to organize/manage community, etc.)
2. Need increased communication across communities, domains, expertise, etc.
3. Continue to encourage development of communities as a NASA priority.